

Crystalline components from the stem bark of *Callistemon lanceolatus*

Renuka Jain^{a*}, Archana Sharma^a, Sapna Rawat^a and Satish C. Jain^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Botany,
University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 055, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : profrajain@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 18 May 2010, accepted 27 August 2010

Abstract : Chemical investigation of pet. ether and benzene solubles from the ethanolic extract of the stem bark of *Callistemon lanceolatus* DC. afforded two novel phenolic acid esters : dotriacontanyl ferulate and 32-hydroxy dotriacontanyl ferulate, triterpenoids : euph-7-en-3 β -ol, 3-O-acetyl ursolic acid, ursolic acid, uvaol-3-acetate, erythrodiol-3-acetate and asiatic acid along with β -sitosterol and its glucoside. This is the first report of the isolation of phenolic acid esters from this genus.

Keywords : *Callistemon lanceolatus*, phenolic acid esters, triterpenoids.

Introduction

Callistemon lanceolatus DC. syn. *C. citrinus* Skeels (Family : Myrtaceae) is a small tree, indigenous to Australia and frequently grown in gardens in India. A survey of literature revealed the isolation of some flavonoids, monoterpenoids and triterpenoids from fruits^{1,2}, flowers¹⁻⁴ and leaves⁵⁻⁹ and tannins from stem bark¹⁰ and seeds¹⁰. In view of the limited phytochemical studies on the stem and no investigation of stem bark, the isolation of constituents from the pet. ether and benzene fractions of the alcoholic extract of stem bark was undertaken.

The stem bark of *C. lanceolatus* DC. was collected from the University Campus, Jaipur and identified in the Department of Botany, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur (Herbarium Sheet No. RUBL 20125). Air-dried and coarsely powdered stem bark (2.5 kg) was extracted exhaustively with ethanol (95%) on a steam bath for 8 h. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure when a dark brown solid (130 g) was obtained. The ethanolic residue on re-extraction with pet. ether and benzene afforded dark brown semi-solids, 22.2 g and 80.0 g respectively, which exhibited a similar TLC profile. These were mixed and column chromatographed over silica gel when elution with solvents of increasing polarity afforded ten crystalline compounds which included two novel phenolic acid esters, six triterpenoids and two steroids. The phenolic acid esters have been isolated for the first time from this genus.

Dotriacontanyl ferulate : Elution with pet. ether : benzene (9 : 1) yielded a yellowish-white solid which on crystallization (CHCl₃-MeOH) afforded white needles, m.p. 70–72 °C. It exhibited IR peaks at 3550 (OH stretching), 1712 (COOR), 1640 (C=C), 1595, 1590, 1500 (aromatic C=C) and 960 cm⁻¹ (*trans* C=C). Its ¹H NMR spectrum displayed downfield doublets at δ 7.58 and 6.32 (*J* 15.9 Hz) assignable to *trans* vinylic protons H-7 and H-8 respectively attached to benzene ring and the *ortho* coupled aromatic protons H-5 and H-6 appeared as doublets at δ 6.93 and 7.06 (*J* 8 Hz). A singlet at δ 7.04 appeared due to C-2 proton on the benzene ring. Other peaks appeared as triplet at δ 0.87 (methyl group), broad singlet at 1.25 (methylene protons), singlet at 3.93 (methoxy), triplet at 4.16 (CH₂O) and broad singlet at 5.84 (phenolic hydroxyl group). In the mass spectrum, peaks appeared at *m/z* 642 (M⁺, C₄₂H₇₄O₄), 627 (M⁺-CH₃), 194 (M⁺-C₃₂H₆₄), 178 (M⁺-C₃₂H₆₄O₂) and 177 (M⁺-C₃₂H₆₅O).

32-Hydroxy dotriacontanyl ferulate : It was obtained as white needles, m.p. 91–93 °C. IR spectrum showed peaks at 3550 (-OH stretching), 1712 (COOR), 1640 (C=C), 1595, 1590, 1500 (aromatic C=C), 1090 (C-O) stretching and 960 *trans* (C=C). In the ¹H NMR spectrum, a pair of downfield doublets at δ 7.54 and 6.24 (*J* 15.6 Hz) for *trans* double bond attached to the benzene ring, doublets at δ 6.88 and 7.02 (*J* 8.1 Hz) for *ortho* coupled aromatic protons and singlet at δ 7.06 for C-2

proton appeared in the downfield region. A singlet at δ 3.90 (methoxy protons) and two triplets at 4.15 and 3.53 for methylene group attached to the ester oxygen (-O-CO-CH₂-) and hydroxyl group (-CH₂-OH) respectively and a broad singlet at δ 1.25 (methylene protons) were also observed. In the mass spectrum, molecular ion peak which was also the base peak appeared at m/z 658 (M^+ , C₄₂H₇₄O₅) and other peaks at m/z 640 (M^+ -H₂O), 627 (M^+ -CH₂OH), 178 (M^+ -C₃₄H₆₄O₂), 177 (M^+ -C₃₂H₆₅O₂) and 136 (M^+ -C₃₄H₆₆O₃).

Dotriacontanyl ferulate : R = H
32-Hydroxy dotriacontanyl ferulate : R = OH

Euph-7-en-3 β -ol : Elution with pet. ether : benzene (1 : 1) followed by crystallization furnished white needles (CHCl₃-MeOH), m.p. 110–112 °C, C₃₀H₅₂O, M^+ 428. It gave characteristic LB test for triterpenoids. It formed an acetate, m.p. 108 °C¹¹.

β -Sitosterol : Elution with pet. ether : benzene (3 : 2), followed by crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture gave white needles, m.p. 135–137 °C. It gave positive LB test for sterols.

3-O-Acetyl ursolic acid : It was eluted with pet. ether : benzene (3 : 2) and crystallized as white needles (C₆H₆-MeOH), m.p. 282–283 °C, C₃₂H₅₀O₄, M^+ 498. It gave positive LB and Noller's test for triterpenoids. Its identity was confirmed by hydrolysis where it gave ursolic acid, m.p. 286–287 °C¹².

Ursolic acid : Elution with pet. ether : benzene (3 : 2) yielded a brown solid which on crystallization afforded white solid (C₆H₆-MeOH), m.p. 286–287 °C¹³, C₃₀H₄₈O₃, M^+ 456. It gave positive tests for triterpenoids, it gave an acetate, m.p. 282–283 °C and methyl ester, m.p. 167–168 °C¹³.

Uvaol-3-acetate : It was eluted with pet. ether : benzene (3 : 2) as a yellowish-white solid and was crystallized as white needling (CHCl₃-MeOH), m.p. 258–260 °C¹⁴, C₃₂H₅₂O₃, M^+ 484. It gave positive LB and Noller's

test for triterpenoids. On hydrolysis it gave uvaol, m.p. 226–228 °C¹⁵.

Erythrodiol-3-acetate : Elution with pet. ether : benzene (1 : 4) yielded a pale yellow solid which on crystallization afforded white powder (CHCl₃-MeOH), m.p. 230–232 °C, C₃₂H₅₂O₃. It gave positive tests for triterpenoids, and on hydrolysis it gave erythrodiol, m.p. 234 °C¹⁶.

Asiatic acid : Elution with benzene : ethyl acetate (4 : 1) yielded a white solid which on crystallization afforded white needles (EtOAc), m.p. 300–305 °C, C₃₈H₄₈O₅. It gave positive tests for triterpenoids and formed a methyl ester, m.p. 225 °C¹⁷.

β -Sitosterol- β -D-glucoside : Elution with ethyl acetate gave an off-white solid which on evaporation crystallized as white granules (MeOH), m.p. 292–293 °C, C₃₅H₆₀O₆, FAB mass 599 (M^+ + Na⁺)¹⁸. It gave positive LB test for sterols and Molisch's test for sugars and did not reduce Fehling's solution. On hydrolysis it gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 135–137 °C.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (SR) is thankful to the CSIR, New Delhi, for financial support.

References

1. L. N. Mishra, F. Hug, A. Ahmad and A. K. Dixit, *J. Ess. Oil Res.*, 1997, **9**, 625.
2. F. M. Hashim, A. M. E. Shamy and A. H. Shehta, *Bull. Fac. Pharm.*, 1982, **19**, 139.
3. K. P. Tiwari, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1972, **42**, 86.
4. P. S. Tandon and K. P. Tiwari, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1970, **57**, 394.
5. S. K. Srivastava, A. Ahmad, N. Jain, K. K. Aggarwal and K. V. Syamasunder, *J. Ess. Oil Res.*, 2001, **13**, 359.
6. M. Lonasmaa, H. S. Puri and C. J. Widen, *Phytochemistry*, 1977, **16**, 185.
7. I. I. Mohmoud, F. A. Mohraram, M. S. A. Marzouk, M. W. Linschered and M. I. Salen, *Pharmazie*, 2002, **57**, 494.
8. E. G. M. Younes, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 221.
9. E. G. M. Younes, *Phytochemistry*, 1975, **14**, 592.
10. L. S. Bhatia, M. S. Bhatia, R. S. Sharma and K. L. Bajaj, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 959.
11. T. Itoh, T. Tamura and T. Mastumoto, *J. Lipids*, 1976, **11**, 434.
12. S. Dev, "CRC Handbook of Triterpenoids", Vol. II, CRC Press, Florida, 1989, p. 287.

Note

- 13 S Huneck and G Snatzke, *Chem Ber* , 1965 **98**, 120
- 14 P Sengupta A K Dey, J Mukherjee, S Ghosh and K Ganesh Das, *J Indian Chem Soc* , 1969, **66**, 775
- 15 A Zurcher, O Jeger and L Ruzicka, *Helv Chem Acta*, 1954, **37**, 2145
- 16 Y C Awasthi and C R Mitra, *Phytochemistry* 1968, **7**, 637
- 17 P T Thuong W Y Jin J Lee, R Seong Y M Lee, Y H Seong, K Song and K Bae, *Arch Pharm Res* , 2005 **28** 1135
- 18 R Jain, S Alam, R Arora and S C Jain *J Med Arom Pl Sci* 1998, **20** 740

